

Detection of Thyroid Hormone Deficiency in Neonate Cord BloodSurya Kantha Bugge¹, Mohd Munawar Ali Khan², Aseel Khalid Suliman Al-Duraibi³¹Associate Professor, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.²Post Graduate Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India³General Practitioner, Saudi Arabia.

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Infants with Congenital Hypothyroidism (CH) may present with subtle or nonspecific clinical signs initially, as residual maternal thyroid hormones can temporarily mask symptoms.**Materials and Methods:** 3ml of Cord blood was drawn after the 3rd stage of labour and Thyroid Function tests were performed by Electrochemiluminescence method, Patients were recalled if the Thyroid stimulating Hormone (TSH) Value was > 60 mIU/L.**Results:** 8 babies had Congenital Hypothyroidism (CH) of which 2 were Downs syndrome babies and 1 baby had heart anomalies. incidence has been calculated to be 1 in 2402 live births, in the period from April 2012 to March 2013 in Qassim region of Saudi Arabia.**Conclusion:** Umbilical cord blood TSH proves to be an effective screening tool in identifying congenital hypothyroidism, thereby preventing mental retardation and other adverse effects associated with untreated CH.**Keywords:** Thyroid stimulating Hormone (TSH), Congenital Hypothyroidism (CH), Screening.

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Introduction

Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is a condition characterized by thyroid hormone deficiency present from birth, which can arise from diverse etiologies including thyroid gland dysgenesis, dysmorphogenesis, or secondary deficiencies in thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). It represents a significant global health concern due to its potential to cause permanent neurodevelopmental deficits if left untreated [1,2].

Recent studies underscore the critical role of early detection through neonatal screening in mitigating the adverse effects of CH. Screening programs utilize advancements in technology for accurate measurement of thyroxine (T4) and TSH levels from small blood samples obtained shortly after birth. These screenings have become standard practice in many developed countries, aimed at identifying affected infants before symptoms manifest [3,4].

Infants with CH may present with subtle or nonspecific clinical signs initially, as residual maternal thyroid hormones can temporarily mask symptoms. Prompt diagnosis within the first few weeks of life and immediate initiation of levothyroxine therapy are crucial to prevent irreversible cognitive impairment and ensure normal neurodevelopmental outcomes.

Research continues to refine diagnostic protocols and therapeutic strategies to optimize outcomes for

infants diagnosed with CH. Modern treatment approaches emphasize maintaining T4 levels within specific ranges during early childhood and normalizing TSH concentrations to support optimal growth and development. Recent studies highlight advancements in therapeutic regimens that aim for more aggressive correction of thyroid hormone levels, potentially enhancing long-term neurocognitive outcomes in affected individuals.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in achieving universal newborn screening for CH worldwide. Variability in screening protocols and access to healthcare infrastructure continue to impact the timely diagnosis and management of CH, particularly in underserved regions.

Ongoing research and clinical efforts are focused on improving screening technologies, refining treatment guidelines, and enhancing global awareness to ensure early identification and effective management of congenital hypothyroidism. By addressing these challenges, healthcare systems can further reduce the burden of CH and optimize developmental [5].

Causes and Symptoms

Congenital Hypothyroidism (CH) in newborns is mainly due to the absence or underdevelopment of the thyroid gland. Less commonly, the thyroid is present but dysfunctional. Initially asymptomatic,

affected newborns may later show lethargy, poor appetite, low muscle tone, constipation, hoarse crying, and umbilical hernia. Untreated, CH leads to developmental delays, intellectual disability, and distinctive physical features.

Screening and Incidence: Screening programs for CH started in 1974 in Quebec and Pittsburgh and are now widespread globally. In North America, over 5 million newborns are screened annually, identifying about 1,400 cases. The incidence of CH ranges from 1 in 3,000 to 1 in 4,000 newborns, with higher rates in Hispanic populations and lower rates in Black populations. Females are twice as likely to be affected as males, with increased risk in Down syndrome infants.

Nutritional and Maternal Factors: Iodine deficiency, a common cause of preventable mental retardation, is still a concern despite supplementation efforts. Recent evidence indicates possible iodine deficiency in some North American pregnant women, potentially due to dietary changes. Selenium and iron deficiencies also impact thyroid function and neurological development. Adequate iodine supplementation during pregnancy can normalize thyroid function in mothers and newborns.

Diagnostic Protocols and Treatment: In Saudi Arabia, SAMSO hospitals use cord blood thyroxin (CB-TT4) screening, with additional thyroid-stimulating hormone (CB-TSH) testing for low TT4 levels. From 1990 to 2007, 96,015 newborns were screened, detecting 26 cases of primary CH, typically starting treatment at 8.2 days with thyroxin. Adjusted protocols since 2004 have reduced recall rates without missing CH cases.

Impact of Maternal Hypothyroidism: Maternal thyroid hormone (TH) is crucial for foetal development, particularly in early pregnancy. The foetal thyroid system matures by delivery, but maternal-foetal hypothyroidism can severely impair neurodevelopment. Early and adequate postnatal treatment generally results in normal cognitive outcomes for infants with CH.

Additional Considerations: CH screening is more prevalent than for conditions like phenylketonuria. Optimal screening and follow-up methods for low T4 but normal TSH infants remain under review. CH often co-occurs with congenital anomalies, especially heart defects, though routine screening for these anomalies lacks consensus

Materials and Methods

Screening Method: In Saudi Arabia, where approximately 95% of mothers deliver in hospitals and are discharged within 24 hours, the screening program utilizes umbilical cord serum for detecting thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) to maximize diagnostic benefits. At delivery, 4 ml of cord blood

is collected from the placental side before placental delivery. Serum is immediately separated and stored at -20°C until transported in insulated containers to the Regional Central Laboratory. Elevated or inconclusive TSH results prompt retesting for confirmation. Neonates with elevated TSH are referred to secondary healthcare for further management and follow-up. Parents of confirmed congenital hypothyroidism cases receive education, counselling, and management plans, with potential referral to tertiary healthcare if necessary.

Umbilical Blood Sampling Procedure: After the approval of the Institutional ethics committee, the medical staff at Maternity and Child Health hospital Buraidah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia, used a 5 ml syringe to collect 3 ml of cord blood within 2-3 minutes of birth. They then transferred the collected blood into a plain glass tube with a red cap. Afterward, they communicated with the parents about the test procedure and the protocol for notifying them of any abnormal results. The staff ensured that all accompanying specimen documents were accurate and complete. The blood was then transported to the hospital laboratory at room temperature. If the hospital laboratory could not process the samples immediately, the samples were stored at 4°C until they could be transported to the regional laboratory.

Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) Assay

- TSH is assayed using the Delfia Electro chemiluminescent (ECL) method.
- ECL utilizes a ruthenium (II)-tris(bipyridyl) [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ complex and tripropylamine (TPA) for chemiluminescent reaction.
- The assay involves:
 - Generating reactive species at an electrode surface upon applying voltage.
 - Reaction of TPA and ruthenium complex to emit light, proportional to TSH concentration.
 - Use of streptavidin-coated micro particles for binding and separation of immune complexes.
 - Calibration curve established with known standards for quantitative analysis.

Advantages of ECL Technology

- Stable, non-isotopic labelling allows for liquid reagent convenience.
- High sensitivity with short incubation times for rapid results.
- Wide dynamic range minimizes dilutions and handling costs.
- Applicable to diverse analytes, supporting menu expansion in diagnostics.

Assay Principles

- Competitive, sandwich, and bridging principles adapted based on analyte size and type.

- Competitive: Used for low molecular weight analytes like T3.
- Sandwich: Applied to larger analytes such as TSH.
- Bridging: Designed for detecting antibodies (e.g., IgG, IgM).

Study Design Overview

Study Type: This is an observational study using a cross-sectional design.

Setting: The study was conducted at the Maternal and Child Hospital (MCH) in Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

Duration: The data was abstracted from medical records of neonates born between January 2011 and December 2012. The specific study period for sample data collection was from April 2012 to March 2013.

Sample: A total of 19,219 neonates born during the study period were included. The study used consecutive sampling to abstract information from the medical records.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- Newborns at MCH tested and recorded for CB-TSH and CB-TT4 between April 2012 and March 2013. Were included in the study
- Newborns at MCH not tested and recorded for CB-TSH and CB-TT4 during the specified period were Excluded.

Data Collection

Year	Month	Samples Done	Cases >30 mIU/L	Cases >60 mIU/L
2012	April	1697	36	3
2012	May	1711	23	4
2012	June	1714	26	5
2012	July	1898	43	4
2012	August	1733	6	8
2012	September	2237	45	13
2012	October	1672	25	6
2012	November	1689	4	3
2012	December	1638	4	0
2013	January	1638	4	0
2013	February	1613	23	9
2013	March	1617	44	17

Table 2 : The neonate history .

No.	File Number	Height [Cm]	Weight [Kg's]	Sex	Nationality [S=Saudi]
1	7198	33	4.34	F	S
2	105893	35	3	F	S
3	165754	47	4.3	F	S
4	164662	31	5	F	S
5	163390	37	3.5	M	S
6	161627	32	4	M	S
7	67841	27	3.75	F	S
8	231	23	2.8	F	S

- Informed consent was obtained from MCH for medical record abstraction and data collection.
- Data was collected anonymously to maintain patient confidentiality.
- A structured questionnaire was used to gather information on maternal obstetric history, neonate birth history, and cord blood analysis results related to hypothyroidism.

Data Analysis

- Data entry and analysis were performed using Microsoft Excel.
- Descriptive statistics were used to examine the distribution of each study variable (mean, median, standard deviation).
- Results were presented using tables, histograms, pie charts, and line graphs.

Results

Cord Blood Test Results (April 2012 - March 2013)

- Total Cord Blood Samples Tested: 19,219
- Cases with TSH 30-60 mIU/L: 559
- Cases with TSH >60 mIU/L: 70
- Confirmed Congenital Hypothyroidism Cases: 8
- **Incidence Rate:** 1 in 2,402 live births

This study provides valuable data on the prevalence of congenital hypothyroidism (CH) in the Qassim region, highlighting the importance of neonatal screening programs to ensure early detection and treatment.

Table 3: TSH and FT4 Levels from Umbilical Cord and Babies After Recall

No.	Gestational Week	Mode of Delivery N= Normal Vaginal C= Cesarean section	History
1	Full term	N	Sister Has Hypothyroidism
2	34 weeks	N	One of the Parent Has Hypothyroidism
3	Full term	C	Ch Mother Has Hypothyroidism
4	Full term	N	Associated With Down Syndrome [Pituitary Cause]
5	32 weeks	N	Associated With Down Syndrome
6	Full term	C	Ch Mother Has Hypothyroidism
7	Early delivery Bleeding (31 week)	C	Heart Anomalies
8	3 rd Trimester	N	Hypothyroidism

Statistics:

- **Mean (Umbilical Cord):** TSH = 87.625, FT4 = 6.86875
- **Mean (After Recall):** TSH = 63.9713, FT4 = 8.44
- **Standard Deviation (Umbilical Cord):** TSH = 35.0018, FT4 = 4.78711

- **Standard Deviation (After Recall):** TSH = 49.7394, FT4 = 10.1646

This table provides a comprehensive overview of the TSH and FT4 levels for neonates from umbilical cord samples and after recall, highlighting cases of confirmed congenital hypothyroid as well.

No	File Number	From Umbilical Cord		From The Babies After Recall	
		TSH mIU/L (0.2 - 7.2)	FT4 pmol/L (12 - 28)	TSH mIU/L (0.270 - 7.20)	FT4 pmol/L (12 - 28)
1	128112	> 100	30.46	4.11	24.44
2	128109	93.3	16.4	2.74	19.09
3	8010	100	14.87	4.13	20.96
4	43696	64.1	16.96	5.13	19.07
5	141993	> 100	15.49	46.65	16.82
6	27192	64.26	14.27	41.25	14.33
7	151682	0.727	10.18	6.53	17
8	40096	61.06	14	3.45	18.98
9	117537	> 100	21.77	3.51	18.16
10	511	6.13	15.67	33.23	16.22
11	1176509	41.85	9.13	4.91	19.42
12	154439	86.82	19.87	5.14	15.01
13	4892	73.28	11.62	2.75	22.1
14	5116	34.08	9.91	5.6	19.75
15	108804	> 100	12.5	3.19	16.7
16	19393	> 100	14.52	2	22.23
17	1987	> 100	9	6.54	18.8
18	234994	68.46	13.74	7.45	14.12
19	234849	72.99	19.22	4.32	20.51
20	7378	67.61	16.8	6.94	17.31
21	316	> 100	19.86	4.46	19.63
22	129474	> 100	18.51	3.75	27.33
23	8252	63.58	18.68	3.3	22.57
24	5187	3.79	15.7	Normal	
25	33948	83.24	28.19	2.63	19.82
26	112132	71.49	13.14	2.38	17.93
Confirmed Congenital Hypothyroid					
27	7198	100	11.5	5.45	30.05
28	105893	100	16.45	5.02	17.22
31	165754	100	2	100	0.9

32	164662	1	5	1.3	4.7	
33	163390	100	4	100	2	
34	161627	100	5	100	1.75	
35	67841	100	7	100	6.9	
36	231	100	4	100	4	
		87.625	6.86875	63.9713	8.44	Mean
		35.0018	4.78711	49.7394	10.1646	SD

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Comparison Between **Cord Blood** TSH And After **Recall 5 Days Later From The Neonates**
 [Confirmation of CH with TSH values derived on day 5 of neonate is the preferred screening protocol [32]]

The normal range of TSH in human serum is set at 0.2 - 7.2 mIU/L [26] and the Free T4 at 12-28 pmol/L As performed by the [Delfia – Finland] Electrochemiluminescence principle at MCH Buraydah Al Qassim

Comparison between **Cord blood** at delivery and Recall after 5 days **Venous sample**
 Free T4 levels in the 8 confirmed congenital hypothyroidism Babies

Discussion

Neonatal Thyroid Screening

Numerous studies worldwide have investigated neonatal thyroid screening, proposing various TSH cut-off values in cord serum to diagnose hypothyroidism. However, no reports have specifically examined the thyroid status of pregnant mothers and their neonates in the Qassim region. Our study provides novel insights into this area.

Prevalence of Congenital Hypothyroidism in Industrialized Countries

In industrialized countries, the birth prevalence of congenital hypothyroidism ranges from 1 in 3500 to 1 in 4000 live newborns:

- **United Kingdom:** 1 in 3937 (Grant, 1988)
- **North America:** 1 in 3700 (Willi, 1991)
- **France:** 1 in 4041 (Dhondt, 1991)
- **Australia:** 1 in 4253 (Special Report, 1983)
- **New Zealand:** 1 in 4867 (Special Report, 1983)

Data from 14 European countries show a collective birth prevalence of 1 in 3598, with significant inter-country variation from 1 in 2860 in the Netherlands to 1 in 5770 in Austria (Delange, 1998). These variations may be due to differences in sample sizes and screening protocols.

Prevalence in the Asian Region

Reported birth prevalence in the Asian region varies significantly:

- **Hong Kong:** 1 in 2903 (Low, 1986) [6].

- **Thailand:** 1 in 3843 (Rajatanavin, 1993) [7].
- **China:** 1 in 4584 (Zhang, 1993) [8].
- **Singapore:** 1 in 2007 (Joseph, 1991) [9].
- **Pakistan:** 1 in 1000 (Akhani, 1989) [10].
- **India:** 1 in 2481 (Desai, 1987) [11].

Local studies show:

- **Harun (1992):** 1 in 2410 [12].
- **Wu et al. (1999):** 1 in 3666 [13].
- **Amar (1997):** 1 in 2983 [14].

Pooled data suggest a birth prevalence of 1 in 3093 for the South East Asian region (Amar, 1997).

Comparison with Qassim Region

The birth prevalence of congenital hypothyroidism appears higher in Asian countries, including Saudi Arabia, compared to Europe or America. Studies from the United Kingdom and the USA also indicate higher prevalence rates among Asians and Orientals, respectively.

In our observations in Buraydah, Qassim, there were 8 confirmed congenital hypothyroidism cases out of 19,219 births, yielding an incidence of 1 in 2402. This is higher than the 1 in 3573 incidence reported by Nasir A.M et al. (2011) [15] for the Qassim region and the 1 in 3292 incidence for the whole of Saudi Arabia.

Possible Reasons for Increased Prevalence

1. **Consanguinity:** Higher rates of consanguineous marriages in the region may contribute to the increased prevalence.

However, most cases in these studies were due to thyroid dysgenesis rather than inherited defects. [16,17]

2. **Transient Primary Hypothyroidism:** Iodine deficiency may also explain the increased prevalence .
3. **Genetic Factors:** The higher prevalence may reflect the true genetic situation in the region.

Types of Congenital Hypothyroidism Identified

In our study, we identified several types of congenital hypothyroidism (CH) based on biochemical profiles and clinical evaluations:

1. **Primary Hypothyroidism due to Thyroid Dysgenesis:** Five out of eight children had high TSH levels in both cord blood and venous blood on day 5, with low free T4 levels in both samples. This pattern suggests primary hypothyroidism due to thyroid dysgenesis [18]
2. **Thyroid Hormone Resistance:** Two infants were diagnosed with congenital hypothyroidism despite normal functioning of the thyroid and pituitary glands. Their TSH levels were slightly elevated (5.4 and 5.02 mIU/L), and free T4 levels were borderline high (30.05 and 17.22 pmol/L on recall). This condition, known as thyroid hormone resistance, requires clinical and radiological evaluations to confirm the diagnosis [19].
3. **Secondary Hypothyroidism or Central Hypothyroidism:** One infant had low TSH levels (1 mIU/L in cord blood, 1.3 mIU/L in venous blood) and normal to low free T4 levels (5 pmol/L in cord blood, 4.7 pmol/L in venous blood). This pattern indicates secondary hypothyroidism or central hypothyroidism, where there is a failure of the pituitary gland to produce adequate TSH [20].
4. **Association with Down Syndrome:** Two out of the eight confirmed cases of CH were found to have Down syndrome. This association has been observed in other studies as well [21] (22). A study conducted in Riyadh reported a similar observation, where two out of 81 confirmed CH cases also had Down syndrome [22].

Screening and Diagnostic Procedures

Our study underscores the importance of regional screening programs equipped with pediatricians, laboratory technicians, and appropriate scientific and technical support across Saudi Arabia [22]. These programs have been instrumental in effectively identifying cases of congenital hypothyroidism.

Diagnostic procedures include:

- **Thyroid Scans:** Used to identify the etiology of hypothyroidism, particularly in cases suspected of thyroid dysgenesis.
- **Perchlorate Discharge Test:** Conducted in patients with suspected dysmorphogenesis to further confirm the diagnosis.
- **Treatment with L-Thyroxine:** Infants confirmed with CH are initially treated with L-thyroxine at doses of 10-15 ug/kg/day, which is adjusted based on clinical and biochemical responses. [22,18]

Conclusion

Umbilical cord blood TSH proves to be an effective screening tool in identifying congenital hypothyroidism, thereby preventing mental retardation and other adverse effects associated with untreated CH. It is crucial to implement strategies to encourage rural populations, who may deliver babies at home, to seek medical assistance promptly for neonatal screening. This proactive approach aims to prevent long-term cognitive impairments and improve overall quality of life for affected children.

Advances in automation of hormone assays have led to frequent adjustments in TSH and free T4 reference values. Standardization of these values with robust quality control measures is essential for accurate diagnosis and management of congenital hypothyroidism.

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